

TECHNOLOGY OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY
SCHOOL CHILDREN BY MEANS OF GAMIFICATION

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Abstract. Theoretical issues are considered: the concept of gamification, its essential features and distinctive features for use in school; motivation issues. In addition, the work identifies some differences between gamification and other gaming practices. An algorithm for implementing gamification techniques is presented using the example of the Classcraft service in the process of developing the language competence of middle-school students.

Keywords: gamification, language competence, algorithm for implementing gamification in foreign language teaching.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a specific global virtual gaming media space has been formed in the network educational content. Digital educational content, the use of various educational information resources and applications are radically changing the conceptual approach to the use of games as a component of learning. In the context of the educational system, the term "gamification" has appeared, which, however, cannot be fully identified with the concept of a game. Unlike other gaming practices, gamification does not have an imitative nature of activity, and, with unchanged educational content, makes it possible to qualitatively modify the way of organizing educational activities [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Gamification is a relatively new technology for foreign language education, so it has not been sufficiently studied in terms of teaching methods, but at the same time, this technology contains a wide educational potential. In the last decade, gamification has acquired promising lines of development in the structure of foreign language classes in school conditions.

Based on the definition of the term "gamification", we can imagine this technology as a set of user-oriented game elements in a non-game context. It can be recognized that gamification in education is the implementation of game elements of modern online games, contributing to the motivation of students and the achievement of practical educational goals in the course of studying a foreign language.

The relevance of the issue and the analysis of scientific literature on the research problem allows us to formulate a number of contradictions. Firstly, there is no doubt about the need for the active introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process, ensuring the successful development of foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) of students, but, on the other hand, it must be noted that there is insufficient attention to these technologies, which contribute to the formation of high motivation of students and the fascination of the process of foreign language education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis of relevance and identified contradictions, it is possible to formulate the goal of the work in several research planes:

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- clarification of the essential psychological and distinctive didactic characteristics of the concept of gamification as an innovative technology that promotes the development of components of foreign language communicative competence of students;
- correlation and justification of correlating points of educational and game tasks of gamification, allowing to develop the internal motivation of students to perform priority educational tasks in the process of teaching a foreign language;
- determination of the place and role of gamification in the structure of development of the language component of foreign language communicative competence of students;
- development and implementation in the process of development of the language component of foreign language communicative competence of students of methods of implementing gamification in foreign language lessons, adapted to modern educational conditions.

As for gamification, it involves the creation of a game shell that is used in a non-game context and is aimed at achieving real goals. The essence of the difference between gamification and other game practices is that reality remains reality and does not turn into a game, and the introduction of game settings into the student's system of operations is associated with this reality.

The first stage is considered as pedagogical planning and includes several sub-stages in accordance with the presented hierarchy:

1. setting educational goals and presenting planned results, topics included in the gamification process in the context of teaching a foreign language, identifying problematic topics, gaps in students' knowledge within the framework of introducing the technology;
2. choosing the form of work (an online game based on information and communication technologies, or using gamification techniques selected by the teacher), developing the implementation of the technology and methods for monitoring independent work (discussing with the student preferences and interests regarding online games);
3. developing a game scenario, rules and instructions, modeling an online game, determining the duration of the game, implementation deadlines, the feasibility of including certain gamification techniques in the educational process (for example, the possibility of disqualification, deprivation of points, a prize fund, etc.).

The second stage involves determining the psychotype of the student-player, identifying the type of players (out of 4 possible in accordance with the rules of the game) for each student individually based on the Bartle test [1].

The third stage, directly related to the gamification process, involves conducting a quest (online game), using individual gamification elements in order to master and improve language competence [4].

The fourth stage involves monitoring the educational process of gamification, the possibility of its adjustment and reflection of the planned results, the emotional component and motivation of students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of theoretical and practical research, the positive influence of digital virtual worlds and interactive electronic products on the process of teaching a foreign language in the context of school education was revealed. An algorithm for using gamification techniques to develop the language component of foreign language communicative competence of students at the middle stage of school education was identified, structured and tested.

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